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Abstract

This deliverable report provides information on the development of the GraspOS tools and services, which are federated in the GraspOS infrastructure. The report also contains references to the code repositories and the documentation websites of the respective software packages. This is the second (and final) version of the respective deliverable providing refinements and updates to everything reported in D3.2, that has been submitted in August 2024.

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Abbreviation List

- **AI:** Artificial Intelligence
- **API:** Application Programming Interface
- **APP:** Assessment Protocol Portfolio (service by CWTS)
- **ARC:** "Athena" Research Center
- **CC-BY:** Creative Commons Attribution license
- **CiTO:** Citation Typing Ontology
- **CEC:** Citation Extractor and Classifier (tool by UniBo)
- **CEX:** Citation Extractor (tool by UniBo)
- **CIC:** Citation Intent Classifier (tool by UniBo)
- **CoARA:** Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
- **CRIS:** Current Research Information System
- **CS:** Computer Science
- **CWTS:** Centre for Science and Technology Studies - Universiteit Leiden
- **DAS:** Data Availability Statements
- **DB:** DataBase
- **DBLP:** Digital Bibliography & Library Project
- **DOAB:** Directory of Open Access Books
- **DOI:** Digital Object Identifier
- **DORA:** Declaration on Research Assessment
- **EOSC:** European Open Science Cloud
- **FAIR:** Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
- **FoS:** Fields of Science
- **HPC:** High Performance Computing
- **IIS:** Information Inference Service (tool by OpenAIRE)
- **KER:** Key Exploitable Result
- **LLM:** Large Language Model
- **OA:** Open Access
- **OAI-PMH:** Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
- **OCDM:** OpenCitations Data Model
- **OI4RRA:** Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment
- **ORCID:** Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier
- **OS:** Open Science
- **OS-aware RRA:** Open-Science-aware Responsible Research Assessment
- **OSM:** Open Science Monitoring
- **PoC:** proof of concept
- **QoS:** Quality of Service

- **PID:** Persistent Identifier
- **PRISM:** Peer Review Information Service for Monographs
- **RAiD:** Research Activity Identifier
- **RDF:** Resource Description Framework
- **REST:** Representational State Transfer
- **RRA:** Responsible Research Assessment
- **SDE:** Scholarly Data Enrichment
- **SKG-IF:** Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework
- **SSH:** Social Sciences and Humanities
- **TRUBA:** Turkish National e-Science e-Infrastructure.
- **TSV:** Tieteellisten Seurain Valtuuskunnasta (Federation of Finnish Learned Societies)
- **UI:** User Interface
- **UNIBO:** University of Bologna

DRAFT

1. Executive Summary

Research assessment processes are important for informing decisions on funding, hiring, promotions, and strategic planning within the research community. However, conducting research assessment is challenging, especially when striving to prioritise responsible practices and integrate Open Science aspects.

GraspOS developed, enhanced, and delivered practical tools and services to support research assessment processes, paving the way for a reform towards OS-aware Responsible Research Assessment (OS-aware RRA). These resources comprise key components of the federated infrastructure that the GraspOS project is implementing.

This report supplements the release of the final versions of the tools and services federated in GraspOS. More specifically, it provides the necessary background to help readers understand the landscape of tools and services which are relevant to the project, introducing key terminology and a classification scheme for such resources that takes into consideration their main functionalities and use cases. Additionally, the report offers an overview of the current GraspOS-federated tools and services, and outlines basic implementation details as well as the planned development activities beyond the end of the project. Finally, the report provides references to all code repositories and supporting materials, serving as a comprehensive entry point for anyone interested in accessing the source code and relevant documentation.

2. Introduction and Background

Research assessment processes, which are used to evaluate the quality, impact, and significance of research activities and products/outputs, are essential for informing decisions related to funding, hiring, promotions, and strategic planning within the broader research community. However, conducting research assessment can be tedious and time-consuming for evaluators, who are often overwhelmed by other research-related responsibilities. Moreover, prioritising responsible and inclusive evaluation practices while appropriately integrating Open Science (OS) activities is challenging, and evaluators would greatly benefit from guidance. To this end, GraspOS developed, enhanced, and delivered a suite of practical tools and services designed to address these challenges and facilitate OS-aware Responsible Research Assessment (OS-aware RRA).

More specifically, GraspOS delivered a federated infrastructure designed to aggregate open resources that facilitate the implementation of necessary policy reforms. Figure 1 presents a high-level conceptual architecture of the infrastructure. As highlighted in the figure, tools and services represent key components of the infrastructure. The GraspOS infrastructure

enhances the discoverability of its tools and services primarily through its meta-catalogue¹, which is designed to maintain rich metadata for each tool and service and leverages this information to provide advanced search and filtering functionalities for the end users. The basic metadata are stored in two core catalogues dedicated to tools² and services³, which are synchronised with the EOSC Resource Hub of the EOSC EU node⁴ and, in addition, offer separate user interfaces. Additional enrichments, which further enhance discoverability, are stored in the central meta-catalogue database (co-hosted with the infrastructure front-end). More details on the architectural design of the GraspOS infrastructure can be found in Deliverables D4.1⁵ and D4.2⁶, while information related to its implementation along with some key updates can be found in Deliverables D4.3⁷, D4.4⁸, and D4.5⁹.

Figure 1 Overview of the GraspOS infrastructure

At this point, it is essential to explain the main difference between tools and services according to the conventions we have adopted for the project. Both terms refer to types of software; however, each serves a different purpose and has distinct characteristics. We use the term **“tool”** to refer to a stand-alone piece of software, such as a script, executable, or even workflow, which can be used by installing and executing it locally on a computer or

¹ GraspOS meta-catalogue: <https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/catalogue/>

² GraspOS Tools Catalogue: <https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-tools/>

³ GraspOS Services Catalogue: <https://graspos-services.athenarc.gr/>

⁴ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/all>

⁵ GraspOS Deliverable 4.1: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8302197>

⁶ GraspOS Deliverable 4.2: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13618531>

⁷ GraspOS Deliverable 4.3: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10475567>

⁸ GraspOS Deliverable 4.4: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13617815>

⁹ GraspOS Deliverable 4.5: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.17339531>

computational cluster owned by the end user to conduct a particular type of analysis and/or produce data. The term “**service**”, on the other hand, refers to a piece of software that provides a set of functions or features for the end user, typically hosted on a remote server and accessed via a web interface or API. Essentially, the service provider aims to offer it on a 24/7 basis, guaranteeing the respective Quality of Service (QoS), such as service availability.

Any individual using a GraspOS tool or service is, by definition, considered a GraspOS infrastructure end user. Accessing a GraspOS service, of course, does not in general require any special technical skills or computational resources from the end user. On the other hand, using a GraspOS tool requires technical expertise for installation and deployment, as well as computational resources from the end user. Since all GraspOS services are open source, it is also possible for stakeholders to deploy an instance of a GraspOS service in another location.

Additionally, it is worth mentioning that the first list of tools and services, to be included in the GraspOS infrastructure, was created based on the competencies of the project’s technical partners. However, the GraspOS infrastructure is planned to act as an open and evolving ecosystem; hence, the list of assessment resources currently included in the infrastructure will be subject to changes in the future, based on a clear resource inclusion policy that will be published shortly after the completion of the project (relevant insights can be found in D4.2¹⁰). During the project implementation phase, the focus was on making an initial set of tools and services available and testing them in practice. In this report, we discuss this set of resources. Of course, many other similar tools and services exist, some of which may be registered to the GraspOS Tools & Services Catalogues in the near future.

3. Tools and Services Classification

According to its project plan, GraspOS primarily focuses on tools and services for data enrichment and Open Science monitoring, while also placing significant emphasis on data services that support research assessment processes, particularly those related to OS-aware RRA. In this context, a preliminary classification of the tools and services of interest was introduced in D3.1¹¹ ('Tools & Services Landscape Report') to present the state-of-the-art landscape. Following the publication of that report, GraspOS experts refined the initial classification and developed enhanced schemes for categorising GraspOS tools and services. The next sections describe the respective classification schemes.

¹⁰ GraspOS Deliverable 4.2: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13618530>

¹¹ GraspOS Deliverable 3.1: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8302169>

3.1. Tools Classification Taxonomy

Table 1 summarises the two-level taxonomy currently used by GraspOS for the classification of tools that are relevant to the context of OS-aware RRA.

Table 1 Overview of the GraspOS Tools Classification Taxonomy

Category	Subcategory
Scholarly Data Enrichment (SDE) Tools	(Tools for enrichment with) Missing attributes
	(Tools for enrichment with) Indicators
	(Tools for enrichment with) Missing links & semantics
Open Science Monitoring (OSM) Tools	(Monitoring tools for) Researchers
	(Monitoring tools for) Institutions
	(Monitoring tools for) Countries
	General (monitoring tools)

The **Scholarly Data Enrichment (SDE) category** contains tools designed to enrich scholarly data sources with missing information that is valuable for OS-aware research assessment. The “Missing attributes” subcategory includes tools that support the enrichment of scholarly (meta)data records related to research products and other research-related entities (e.g., institutions, researchers) by adding missing metadata. The “Indicators” subcategory refers to tools aimed at enriching scholarly (meta)data records related to research outputs and other research-related entities (e.g., institutions, researchers) with a variety of metrics and indicators that capture (a) the usage of research products (e.g., article views/downloads, accounting data of research services), (b) their uptake and impact from different perspectives, (c) Open Science uptake, and (d) other types of scientific merit. Finally, the “Missing links & semantics” subcategory contains tools designed to identify missing links between scholarly (meta)data records (e.g., authorship links, citation links, affiliation links) and to address missing semantics of existing links (e.g., contribution roles for authorship links, citation intent).

The **Open Science Monitoring (OSM) category** includes tools offering metrics, indicators, visualisations, information, and evidence that facilitate Open Science (OS) monitoring from various perspectives and at different levels. More specifically, tools in the “Researchers” subcategory focus on monitoring OS practices at the level of individual researchers or

research groups. Similarly, tools in the “*Institutions*” and “*Country*” subcategories focus on OS monitoring at the level of research-performing or funding organisations and at the level of countries, respectively. Finally, a “*General*” subcategory is included for tools that cannot be specifically classified within the previous subcategories (e.g., tools for monitoring openness at the level of research products or services).

3.2. Services Classification Taxonomy

Table 2 summarises the two-level taxonomy currently used by GraspOS for the classification of services that can be valuable in the context of OS-aware RRA.

Table 2 Overview of the GraspOS Services Classification Taxonomy

Category	Subcategory
Scholarly Data Enrichment (SDE) Services	(Services for enrichment with) Missing attributes
	(Services for enrichment with) Indicators
	(Services for enrichment with) Missing links & semantics
OS Monitoring (OSM) Services	(Monitoring services for) Researchers
	(Monitoring services for) Institutions
	(Monitoring services for) Countries
	General (monitoring services)
Data Services	(Generic) Scholarly data resources
	Assessment registries

The explanation for the first two categories - **Scholarly Data Enrichment (SDE)** and **OS Monitoring (OSM) Services**- is identical to the descriptions provided for the respective tool categories presented in Section 3.1. The **Data Services** category contains services that collect and share (meta)data required for research assessment processes. The “*Scholarly data resources*” subcategory encompasses collections of structured information about generic scholarly knowledge, as well as datasets intended for specialised research analytics. These resources provide access to bibliographical metadata and related types of information. The “*Assessment registries*” subcategory, on the other hand, includes registries that collect information on the design and implementation of research assessment activities,

documenting previous evaluation exercises and promoting transparency in assessment processes.

3.3. Connection to Other Classification Schemes

For this deliverable, we have adopted a classification scheme for research-assessment-related tools and services based on their *functionality*. The GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema¹², has been designed to store this classification information in the “*Coverage/assessment_functionalities*” field. However, it is important to note that other complementary classification criteria could also be used for categorising such resources.

A notable example is the classification being developed by CoARA’s OI4RRA working group¹³, which follows a different approach. It focuses on defining the overall architecture of a global ecosystem of open infrastructures that support research assessment. In this approach, the ecosystem’s components are grouped into tiers that represent its key functional layers. This approach adopts a more coarse-grained level of granularity and, in that sense, complementary to the classification presented by GraspOS. The tools and services covered by the GraspOS classification align with several tiers of the OI4RRA classification, while other tiers address components beyond the scope of GraspOS (e.g., PID providers).

¹² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17240298>

¹³ OI4RRA (“Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment”) CoARA working group: <https://coara.eu/coalition/working-groups/wg-towards-open-infrastructures-for-responsible-research-assessment-oi4rra/>

4. GraspOS Tools

This section presents implementation details for the various tools currently hosted by the GraspOS infrastructure. In Section 4.1, we present an overview of all tools, while in Section 4.2, we describe their main functionalities, implementation details, and any deviations from the original plans, and outline future development plans. Finally, in Section 4.3, we include references to the respective code bases and documentation materials.

4.1. Overview

Table 3 provides an overview of the tools currently available through the GraspOS infrastructure. For each tool, the table lists the primary GraspOS partner responsible, as well as the main category under which the tool is classified (refer to Section 3.1 for more details on the classification scheme). All tools listed have been developed or extended as part of the GraspOS project and have an entry in the GraspOS Tools Catalogue.¹⁴ The tools are listed alphabetically by name in the table.

Table 3 Overview of the GraspOS tools

Tool name	Partner resp.	Category
BIP! Citation Classifier	ARC	Scholarly data enrichment > Missing links & semantics
BIP! NDR workflow	ARC	Scholarly data enrichment > Missing links & semantics
BIP! Ranker	ARC	Scholarly data enrichment > Indicators
BIP! Scholar Indicators Calculator	ARC	Scholarly data enrichment > Indicators
Citation Extraction and Classifier	UniBo	Scholarly data enrichment > Missing links & semantics
OpenAIRE IIS Text Mining Modules	OpenAIRE	Scholarly data enrichment > Missing attributes
OPERAS Metrics	OPERAS	OS monitoring > General
SOFTware-Sync	INRIA	Scholarly data enrichment > Missing attributes
SOFTware-Viz	INRIA	OS monitoring > General

¹⁴ GraspOS Tools Catalogue: <https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-tools/> (see also D4.2 & D4.4).

4.2. Main Functionalities and Development

In this section, we describe the main functionalities of each tool, provide implementation details, discuss any deviations from the original plans, and outline future development plans.

4.2.1. BIP! Citation Classifier

Scope & Main Functionalities: The BIP! Citation Classifier is a software library that implements various approaches to classify citations based on their intent. The library relies on the citation context found in scientific publications.¹⁵ Specifically, the text surrounding a reference is used as input, and the library classifies the respective citation according to its intent, based on a well-established citation classification ontology. This information is useful for citation network analysis tasks and the calculation of related indicators.

Implementation: This tool was developed from scratch in the context of the GraspOS project. An initial version was based on a Python implementation of various state-of-the-art algorithms for citation intent classifications (e.g., sciBERT¹⁶). This initial implementation has been extended by incorporating approaches that apply in-context learning and fine-tuning of open Large Language Models (LLMs), which enabled more accurate and nuanced classification of citation intent. In particular, several open LLM families were evaluated under zero-, one-, few-, and many-shot prompting setups to identify optimal configurations for citation intent prediction. Through targeted fine-tuning, the adapted models achieved performance comparable to domain-specific models on benchmark datasets such as SciCite¹⁷. These findings demonstrate the adaptability of general-purpose LLMs to specialized scholarly communication tasks like citation intent classification. This experimental work and its outcomes have been published in a scientific publication¹⁸.

Deviations: No deviations.

Future plans: After the end of the project, the implementation team will focus on leveraging agentic workflows to compute citation intent in a more adaptive and automated way, with the goal of enhancing scalability and interoperability with other GraspOS components.

¹⁵ Currently, only English texts are supported adequately.

¹⁶ Beltagy Iz, Lo Kyle, Cohan Arman: SciBERT: A Pretrained Language Model for Scientific Text. EMNLP-IJCNLP 2019, 10.18653/v1/d19-1371

¹⁷ <https://github.com/allenai/scicite>

¹⁸ P. Koloveas, S. Chatzopoulos, T. Vergoulis, and C. Tryfonopoulos. *Can LLMs Predict Citation Intent? An Experimental Analysis of In-context Learning and Fine-tuning on Open LLMs*. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL)*, 2025.

4.2.2. BIP! NDR Workflow

Scope & Main Functionalities: This software includes the computational workflow used to generate different versions of the BIP! NDR dataset.¹⁹ The dataset provides citation links extracted from Computer Science (CS) conference and workshop publications that lack a DOI. In CS, conference and workshop papers represent major research contributions and carry substantial weight in research assessment processes, compared to other disciplines. However, a considerable number of these papers are not assigned a DOI, hence their citations are missing from widely used citation datasets like OpenCitations and Crossref, which limits the completeness of citation analysis in CS. BIP! NDR aims to alleviate this issue and enhance research assessment within CS by leveraging a workflow that identifies and retrieves CS papers lacking DOIs from the DBLP²⁰ corpus, and by performing text analysis, it extracts citation information directly from their full texts.

Implementation: The BIP! NDR Workflow was developed from scratch in the context of the GraspOS project. It was developed in response to a gap identified by the CS pilot. It is bundled with the BIP! Citation Classifier, which provides citation intent classes for the citations contained in the BIP! NDR dataset. Currently, citation intent classes have been provided for a portion of the dataset and full coverage is expected to be achieved in a future release.

Deviations: No significant deviations (apart from the fact that the citation classes are provided only for part of the BIP! NDR dataset).

Future plans: The implementation team aims to offer citation intent classes for all records in the BIP! NDR dataset within a few months after the end of the project. In addition, improvements to the paper parsing approach will be examined.

¹⁹ BIP! NoDoiRefs (NDR) Dataset: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7962019>

²⁰ DBLP: <https://dblp.uni-trier.de/>

4.2.3. BIP! Ranker

Scope & Main Functionalities: BIP! Ranker is a software library implemented in Apache Spark²¹ that computes a set of impact indicators for research products by leveraging the contents of scholarly knowledge graphs. It currently supports three main categories of citation-based, scientific impact indicators according to their semantics:

- *“Influence”* indicators, which reflect the “total” impact of each research product, i.e., how established it is in general.
- *“Popularity”* indicators, which reflect the “current” impact of each research product, i.e., how popular it is at the query time.
- *“Impulse”* indicators, which reflect the initial momentum that the research product received right after its publication.

Multiple indicators are supported in each category²² and all of them are based on citation network analysis algorithms. More information about the categories, indicators, and semantics can be found in relevant literature.^{23,24} For each indicator, BIP! Ranker provides both the indicator value (e.g., the number of citations for Citation Count) and the corresponding percentile ranking (e.g., “top 1%”), calculated globally and within the relevant scientific field.

The tool can be executed not only locally on a typical computer but also on a computational cluster. The end user gives a citation network as input (i.e., a graph having research products as nodes and citations as edges), and BIP! Ranker then calculates all scores based on the requested indicators. The Spark-based implementation is highly scalable, enabling use even with citation networks containing billions of links.

Implementation: The tool is already in a mature state and has been in production for several years, providing impact-based indicators for various open datasets and APIs available through BIP! Services and the OpenAIRE Graph. As part of the GraspOS project, BIP! Ranker was extended to calculate variations of the already implemented indicators, addressing the specific needs identified by the GraspOS pilots. Specifically, two additional indicators were developed, the field-weighted citation count and the field-weighted impulse, to better account for disciplinary differences in citation practices.

²¹ Apache Spark: <https://spark.apache.org/>

²² Full list: https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/site/indicators#Article-level_Indicators

²³ I. Kanellos, T. Vergoulis, D. Sacharidis, T. Dalamagas, Y. Vassiliou: Impact-Based Ranking of Scientific Publications: A Survey and Experimental Evaluation. IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering (TKDE), 2019

²⁴ T. Vergoulis, S. Chatzopoulos, I. Kanellos, P. Deligiannis, C. Tryfonopoulos, T. Dalamagas: BIP! Finder: Facilitating scientific literature search by exploiting impact-based ranking. Proceedings of the 28th ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management (CIKM), 2019

Deviations: The implementation team did not provide indicators which are sensitive to citation classes (e.g., giving weights to citations according to their intent). Although the concept was tested via small-scale, controlled experiments, further experimentation and significant performance optimisations are needed to operationalise these types of indicators.

Future plans: Future work will explore bundling the tool with other components, such as the BIP! Citation Classifier or the Citation Extractor and Classifier (Section 4.2.5), to operationalise the calculation of indicators that are sensitive to citation classes.

4.2.4. BIP! Scholar Indicators Calculator

Scope & Main Functionalities: This software package provides the necessary implementations for calculating researcher-level indicators (mostly related to citation-based impact) that are being used by the BIP! Scholar service (see Section 5.2.4). In most cases, the author-level indicators are aggregations based on research-product-level citation indicators, like those calculated by BIP! Ranker.

Implementation: The tool existed before the start of the project. In the context of the project, it has been extended to compute additional researcher-level indicators, focusing on indicators that capture aspects related to Open Science. Specifically, taking into account the needs of the project pilots and inputs from WP2 regarding relevant indicator toolboxes, the tool now calculates the number of open-access works that are influential and popular, reflecting the impact and accessibility of a researcher's outputs.

Deviations: No deviations.

Future plans: The implementation team will examine the implementation of additional researcher-level indicators in the future, with a focus on non-publication contributions (e.g., datasets, software).

4.2.5. Citation Extractor and Classifier (CEC)

Scope & Main Functionalities: A tool that performs the automatic extraction and annotation of in-text citations from academic papers, written in English and provided in PDF format. It operates through two steps, described as follows:

1. *Citation Extractor (CEX):* This tool analyses the input PDF and extracts: (a) basic bibliographic metadata (e.g., authors and title); (b) all bibliographic references with metadata (authors, year, title, venue, identifiers); (c) citation sentences containing in-text reference pointers (e.g., “[3]”, “(Doe et al., 2023)”); and, when possible, (d) additional structural information such as section

headings.". All extracted data are returned in JSON and RDF formats compliant with the OpenCitations Data Model (OCDM)²⁵.

2. *Citation Intent Classifier (CIC)*: This step uses a combination of technologies, including Large Language Models (LLM), to classify the semantics of each citation sentence in the JSON output generated during the previous step. The citation functions returned by the software are a subset of those defined in the Citation Typing Ontology (CiTO, <http://purl.org/spar/cito>)²⁶. The output of this step is the original JSON dataset, now enriched with the specification of citation functions associated with each citation.

Implementation: This tool has been developed from scratch to meet the needs of the GraspOS project.

Deviations: No significant deviations from the original plan (apart from renaming as Citation Extractor and Classifier).

Future plans: The tool will be tested more extensively on articles from the social sciences and humanities. In particular, CEX will be extended to process articles with heterogeneous formatting styles, including those with bibliographic references embedded in footnotes. CIC will be trained and extended to identify a larger set of citation functions and to provide explanations about the classification process.

4.2.6. OpenAIRE IIS Text Mining Modules

Scope & Main Functionalities: This information inference tool enriches Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) with automatically inferred metadata, new entities and relations, and information from several data sources (e.g., Publication and Data Repositories, Zenodo, CORDA and other trusted data providers), utilising a flexible big data processing pipeline that supports full-text and metadata mining. The goal of OpenAIRE is to provide an infrastructure for gathering, processing (including deduplication), and providing unified access to research-related data (papers, datasets, researchers, projects, etc.). The goal of OpenAIRE IIS (Information Inference Service) is to provide data/text mining functionality for the OpenAIRE system. In practice, IIS defines data processing workflows that connect various modules, each

²⁵ Daquino, M., Peroni, S., Shotton, D., Colavizza, G., Ghavimi, B., Lauscher, A., Mayr, P., Romanello, M., & Zumstein, P. (2020). The OpenCitations Data Model. In J. Z. Pan, V. Tamma, C. d'Amato, K. Janowicz, B. Fu, A. Polleres, O. Seneviratne, & L. Kagal (Eds), The Semantic Web – ISWC 2020 (Vol. 12507, pp. 447–463). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-62466-8_28

²⁶ Peroni, S. and Shotton, D. 2012. Ontology paper: FaBiO and CiTO: Ontologies for describing bibliographic resources and citations. Web Semant. 17 (December, 2012), 33–43. Available at SSRN: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3198992>

one with well-defined input and output. A high-level overview of IIS can be found in the respective publication.²⁷ IIS ingests data from the aggregated data sources in the OpenAIRE Graph²⁸, runs processing workflows, and produces inferred data which, in turn, is ingested by the Information Space. Current modules include citation extraction (article-data, article-software, product-grant, product-organisations), subject inference covering Fields of Science (FoS) taxonomy and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) classifications, and community context.²⁹

Implementation: The tool existed before the start of the project and is at a mature technology readiness level. As part of the GraspOS project, the tool was maintained and could potentially be bundled with other tools according to the needs of the pilots. Moreover, the pilots exploiting the OpenAIRE CONNECT Gateway benefited from this functionality in the back-end, which aggregates the data used to derive indicators for their research assessment purposes. Extension in the context of GraspOS included methods for the completeness of metadata (e.g., resource types, subjects, licensing typology).

Deviations: The tool was not used as a stand-alone software by the pilots, but was exploited indirectly through the OpenAIRE Graph and CONNECT Gateways, where IIS forms part of the processing pipeline.

Future plans: IIS will continue to be maintained and further developed as part of the ongoing OpenAIRE Graph developments. Several new text-mining modules are in the pipeline, including those for mining and classifying Data Availability Statements (DAS), CREDIT³⁰ Taxonomy statements, and links to pre-registration, as well as other modules supporting Open Science and reproducibility. The software mining module is being extended to cover new domains from Software Heritage, in line with the expansion of its origins³¹, beyond platforms such as Google Code, Bitbucket, Debian, GitHub, SourceForge, and GNU. In parallel, the dataset mining module is being optimised to achieve significantly faster execution, with recent improvements already reducing processing time from around 36 hours to 20, and further optimisation expected to bring this close to half the original runtime. Together, these developments will ensure that IIS remains a core enrichment component of the OpenAIRE infrastructure and continues to support a wide range of future assessment use cases.

²⁷ "Information Inference in Scholarly Communication Infrastructures: The OpenAIREplus Project Experience", *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 38, 2014, 92-99

²⁸ <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/graph-production-workflow/aggregation/>

²⁹ <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/graph-production-workflow/enrichment-by-mining/>

³⁰ <https://credit.niso.org/>

³¹ <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/>

4.2.7. OPERAS Metrics

Scope & Main Functionalities: OPERAS Metrics collects usage and impact metrics related to published Open Access (OA) books and allows their access, display, and analysis from a single access point. By showing the impact of open access books, it also contributes to reinforcing Open Science practices. The key features are the following:

- *Comprehensive Data Collection:* Collects usage metrics from various sources, providing a clear overview of the impact of OA books.
- *Open Source and Community-Driven:* Developed based on the open-source principles, offering an alternative to proprietary usage metrics services and emphasising community involvement.
- *Transparent Processing:* Each metrics is accompanied by an explanation of its data source and collection method.
- *Centrally-Managed Database and Widget:* The metrics are stored in a central database and displayed via a widget embedded on the customer’s site, facilitating real-time interaction and analysis.
- *Flexible Hosting Options:* There is also the option for customers to host the service themselves, with dedicated support by Open Book Publishers.

The software is designed to collect metrics from various sources, and it is divided into different parts, with the most prominent being the Metrics Drivers Wrapper. These drivers serve as entry point components, responsible for gathering data for the system. In addition, there are the “plugins”, which are used to normalise the collected data. Finally, the metrics are combined with the altmetrics and sent to the user interface, where they are displayed with a user-friendly JavaScript widget.

*Figure 2 Simplified OPERAS Metrics Diagram (Image taken directly from:
<https://metrics.operas-eu.org/docs/getting-started>)*

For any interested parties, the primary steps include downloading and installing the Identifier Translation Service, and completing the Altmetrics Registration³² :

- Identifier Translation Service: The Identifier Translation Service is a JSON REST API to a database of publication URIs.³³ This service maps publications to URIs to enable converting from one identifier to another (e.g., info:doi:10.11647/obp.0001, urn:isbn:9781906924010, <https://www.openbookpublishers.com/product/3>) .
- Altmetrics Registration: This software may be useful for users who have implemented an Identifier Translation Service, as it enables the operation of usage-metrics drivers described at <https://metrics.operas-eu.org/docs/getting-started>.

Implementation: The tool has been operational for a number of years and has been adopted by publishers such as Open Book Publishers and Ubiquity Press. Most of its key features, which relate to monitoring the use and impact of OA books, are functional and operational. The main motivation for including Metrics in the GraspOS project was to highlight and value the contribution of OA books in the scholarly landscape. Not many tools offer this monitoring solution, and therefore OPERAS Metrics provides a useful addition for any interested institution to assist their researchers in tracking and reporting on the usage/impact of their OA content. We are aware that this is a priority for SSH researchers in particular, given the dominance of the monograph as an output in the field. As the tool is already operational and has been developed with Open Science principles from its inception, the focus was to further assess its usefulness and identify areas for improvement.

To highlight the benefits of the tool and encourage its adoption, a dedicated training session was organised to showcase how OPERAS Metrics can support the monitoring of Open Access books. The session demonstrated the tool's value for researchers, librarians, and institutional publishers, explaining how it enables transparent tracking of usage and impact. OPERAS Metrics was presented as an open-source database that aggregates data such as reads, downloads, and altmetrics from multiple sources, visualised through an embeddable widget. The second part of the session featured a live technical demonstration, where participants learned how the service collects, processes, and delivers data using APIs, identifier translation, and widgets, including examples of querying and visualising book metrics programmatically.

³² <https://zenodo.org/records/11202909>

³³ https://github.com/hirmeos/identifiers_db

All data and code remain openly available to allow the integration of new data sources and the development of novel widgets with enhanced citation-level visualisation.

Finally, the project established a process for the periodic (annual) extraction of data from the OPERAS Metrics database. To support this process, comprehensive documentation and supporting materials were created and made available on Zenodo³⁴, providing detailed guidance on how to access, use, and analyse the data. These materials include the “OPERAS_Database Copy” (a compressed file containing the database), a database_creation.sh script for recreating the environment, and a README file with step-by-step instructions for data handling and analysis.

Deviations: There is no major deviation from what was expected or agreed to deliver during the project.

Future plans: Future plans include exploring how to make use of the SKG-IF compliant API produced as part of the GraspOS project, to make data and metadata retrieval better aligned with research assessment typology.

4.2.8. SOFTWARE-Sync

Scope & Main Functionalities: Recently, software citations have been recognised as important factors for research assessment processes.³⁵ To date, there is only one international repository with a long-term preservation objective: Software Heritage. However, this repository does not allow for the identification of the contribution types of authors to the code. The extraction of software mentions from publications can help identify who created a source code, who used it and who shared it. This is why INRIA developed a tool allowing the analysis of research publications available in an Open Science repository and to scan them for software mentions. Software mentions in publications can also help correlate a source code with a specific public institution, a specific research laboratory, or authors. Therefore, their analysis can help use open data to evaluate software activity of research entities. At the technical base for this work there are the open source Grobid³⁶ PDF analysis program and the Softcite mentions tool³⁷. Building on this foundation, we developed the synchronisation tool SOFTWARE-Sync, which integrates Grobid and Softcite outputs with metadata from publication repositories.

³⁴ <https://zenodo.org/>

³⁵ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/b69944d4-01f3-11ea-8c1f-01aa75ed71a1>

³⁶ Grobid: <https://github.com/kermitt2/grobid>

³⁷ <https://github.com/softcite/software-mentions>

Implementation: SOFTWARE-Sync has been developed from scratch in the context of the GraspOS project. It was a result of the gap identified by the CS pilot. It is now a standalone hub available to anyone wanting to analyse PDF content in search for software mentions.

Deviations: No deviations.

Future plans: The tool is intended to become part of the services offered by the HAL³⁸ open-archive repository, operating through a notification process that informs researchers and, over time, enables feedback and the creation of a validated list of source codes.

4.2.9. SOFTWARE-Viz

Scope & Main functionalities: This is a basic visualisation tool that offers multiple views of software mentions, relating them to publications, authors, research teams, and institutions. It is built on top of SOFTWARE-Sync.

Implementation: SOFTWARE-Viz was developed from scratch in the context of the GraspOS project. It was developed in response to a gap identified by the CS pilot.

Deviations: No deviations.

Future plans: The development team intends to create a fit-for-purpose tool that will analyse PDFs and metadata from Open Science repositories and deliver exploitable data for a visualisation tool.

³⁸ <https://hal.science/?lang=en>

4.3. Code Repositories and Documentation

Table 4 outlines the code repositories and documentation resources available for the array of tools currently provided through the GraspOS infrastructure.

Table 4 Code repositories and documentation of the GraspOS tools

Tool name	Code repository	Documentation
BIP! Citation Classifier	https://github.com/athenarc/bip-citation-classifier	https://github.com/athenarc/bip-citation-classifier#readme
BIP! NDR workflow	https://github.com/athenarc/bip-ndr-workflow	https://github.com/athenarc/bip-ndr-workflow#readme
BIP! Ranker	https://github.com/athenarc/Bip-Ranker	https://github.com/athenarc/Bip-Ranker#readme
BIP! Scholar Indicators Calculator	https://github.com/athenarc/bip-scholar-indicators	https://github.com/athenarc/bip-scholar-indicators#readme
Citation Extractor and Classifier (formerly: Semantic Citation Classifier)	https://github.com/opencitations/scec	https://github.com/opencitations/scec/blob/main/README.md
OpenAIRE IIS Text Mining Modules	https://github.com/openaire/iis	https://github.com/openaire/iis#readme
OPERAS Metrics	https://github.com/hirmeos	https://metrics.operas-eu.org/docs/getting-started
SOFTWARE-Sync	https://github.com/Samuel-Scalbert/SOFTWARE-Sync	https://github.com/Samuel-Scalbert/SOFTWARE-Sync
SOFTWARE-Viz	https://github.com/Samuel-Scalbert/SOFTWARE-Viz	https://github.com/Samuel-Scalbert/SOFTWARE-Viz

5. GraspOS Services

This section presents implementation details for the various services currently hosted by the GraspOS infrastructure. In Section 5.1, we provide an overview of all services, while in Section 5.2, we elaborate on the main functionalities of each service, provide implementation details, discuss any deviations from the original plans, and outline future development plans. Finally, in Section 5.3, we include references to the respective code bases and documentation materials.

5.1. Overview

Table 5 provides an overview of the services currently available through the GraspOS infrastructure. For each service, the table lists the primary GraspOS partner responsible, as well as the main category under which the service is classified (refer to Section 3.2 for more details on the classification scheme). All services listed have been developed or extended as part of the GraspOS project and are included in the GraspOS Services Catalogue.³⁹ The services are listed alphabetically by name in the table.

Table 5 Overview of the GraspOS services

Service name	Partner resp.	Category
Assessment Protocol Portfolio Registry	CWTS/TSV	Data services > Assessment registries
BIP! DB	ARC	Data services > Scholarly data resources
BIP! NDR	ARC	Data services > Scholarly data resources
BIP! Scholar	ARC	OS monitoring > Researchers
EOSC Accounting for Services	GRNET	OS monitoring > General
EOSC Observatory	OpenAIRE	OS monitoring > Countries
Open Science Observatory	OpenAIRE	OS monitoring > Countries
OpenAIRE Broker	OpenAIRE	Scholarly data enrichment > Missing attributes
OpenAIRE Connect	OpenAIRE	OS monitoring > Institutions
OpenAIRE Graph	OpenAIRE	Data services > Scholarly data resources

³⁹ GraspOS Services Catalogue: <https://graspos-services.athenarc.gr/home> (see also D4.2 & D4.4).

OpenAIRE Metadata Validator	OpenAIRE	Scholarly data enrichment > Indicators
OpenAIRE Monitor	OpenAIRE	OS monitoring > Institutions
OpenAIRE Researcher Profile	OpenAIRE	OS monitoring > Researchers
OpenAIRE ScholeXplorer	OpenAIRE	Data services > Scholarly data resources
OpenAIRE UsageCounts	OpenAIRE	Scholarly data enrichment > Indicators
OpenCitations Data	UniBo	Data services > Scholarly data resources
Openness Profile Registry	CWTS/TSV	Data services > Assessment registries
PRISM	OPERAS	Data services > Scholarly data resources

5.2. Main Functionalities and Development

In this section, we elaborate on the main functionalities of each service, provide implementation details, discuss any deviations from the original plans, and outline future development plans.

5.2.1. Assessment Protocol Portfolio Registry

Scope & Main Functionalities: The Assessment Protocol Portfolio (APP) supports the planning and documentation of research assessment by serving two main functions: it records the agreed approach for a specific assessment event, and it provides a way to register the assessment protocol once the event concludes. In this way, it acts both as a shared resource for conducting the assessment and as a record of its outcomes. An APP is a collaborative, multi-actor digital object that consolidates key information for assessment planning. This includes a readiness self-assessment, values and purpose statements, and the assessment protocol itself, which outlines the agreed assessment approach. During the assessment, the APP is accessible ("locally open") to all participants involved in the event. This can include evaluators, evaluands, and related stakeholders. Afterwards, it can also be made publicly available, balancing the goal of transparency with the need to preserve confidentiality during the process. This staged openness ensures clarity and consistency for evaluators and those being assessed, while protecting sensitive information during the event. When an assessment concludes, the APP can be archived for historical reference. Long-term preservation of assessment planning and assessment protocols promotes transparency, reuse, and mutual

learning, turning the registry into a community resource that informs and inspires the design of future assessment events.

Implementation: The Assessment Protocol Portfolio (APP) Registry, a new service, is part of the SCOPE+i Framework developed for the GraspOS project. In the context of this project, an APP will be implemented via a Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) service point for piloting the service. Each registered protocol will be assigned a persistent identifier and a metadata record, to ensure long-term accessibility and make the information suitable for public use. While a user interface is available for administering access and compiling content (useful for smaller tasks), the service is ideally integrated into local platforms via API.

Deviations: The scope was expanded to enable collaborative documentation throughout the assessment process. This documentation serves as a record of planning and agreements related to the assessment approach, and can be published alongside the assessment protocol. During the project, we experimented with different service models. The initial model⁴⁰ included an assessment portfolio service, which was separate from a protocol registry. Together with the Openness Profile, this meant three services in total. The current model streamlines functionality and anticipated usage into two services. For further details on this updated service model, see D2.3 SCOPE+i Framework (forthcoming).

Future plans: The current SCOPE+i services—comprising the Openness Profile Registry and the Assessment Protocol Portfolio Registry—already incorporate a mapping to the existing RAiD metadata schema elements used to describe an assessment event. Looking ahead⁴¹, we propose extending the RAiD metadata schema to better accommodate the specific requirements of research assessment. The introduction of additional fields would enable more comprehensive cataloguing of assessment projects, including details on the scope of the assessment as well as the data sources and metrics employed. Such an extension would strengthen interoperability and support greater transparency and comparability across assessment practices.

⁴⁰ Tatum, C., Zeynep, A., Vergoulis, T., Polonen, J., Ivanović, D., Nordling, J., Sipola, T., Koivisto, E., & Mira Söderman, M. (2024). GraspOS Deliverable 2.4 "OSAF Specifications for Pilots" (Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14066174>

⁴¹ see D2.3 SCOPE+i Framework (forthcoming).

5.2.2. BIP! DB

Scope & Main Functionalities: BIP! DB is a data service that offers citation-based impact indicators for more than 295 million research products, including scientific publications, software, datasets, and other scholarly outputs. For each research product, the service exposes these indicators (through open APIs and datasets⁴²) calculated by the BIP! Ranker tool, building citation networks based on data retrieved by the OpenAIRE Graph.

Implementation: The service was already in a mature phase when the project started. Within the context of GraspOS, basic maintenance and targeted extensions were carried out based on feedback from the GraspOS pilots. In particular, two additional field-weighted indicators (citation count and impulse) are now provided in BIP! DB (dataset and API), computed by BIP! Ranker. Finally, similarly to other GraspOS data services, the API was adapted and extended to ensure compatibility with the GraspOS data model and API specification.

Deviations: No deviations.

Future plans: BIP! DB will continue to receive regular updates. Moreover, additional indicators are expected to be added with particular emphasis on metrics reflecting non-publication contributions such as datasets and software.

5.2.3. BIP! NDR

Scope & Main functionalities: BIP! NDR is a data service that identifies and retrieves Open Science papers lacking Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) from the DBLP corpus. Through text analysis, it extracts citation information directly from their full texts. In the field of Computer Science, conference and workshop papers are important contributions, carrying substantial weight in research assessment processes, compared to other disciplines. However, a considerable number of these papers are not assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), hence their citations are not reported in widely used citation datasets like OpenCitations and Crossref, limiting the scope of citation analysis. BIP! NDR aims to alleviate this issue and enhance the research assessment processes within the field of Computer Science.

Implementation: BIP! NDR is a new service developed as part of the GraspOS project. The latest version (v1.10) contains almost 4.3M citations made by approximately 211K open access Computer Science conference or workshop papers that, according to DBLP, do not have a DOI. In addition, a subset of these citations is further categorized based on the indent. As with other GraspOS data services, the API is extended to ensure compatibility with the GraspOS

⁴² BIP! DB API & datasets: <https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/site/data>

data model and API specification. The dataset is being updated when new versions of the DBLP dataset are released.

Deviations: No significant deviations (apart from the fact that the citation classes are provided only for part of the dataset).

Future plans: The implementation team aims to offer citation intent classifications for all records in the BIP! NDR dataset within a few months after the project's completion. Regular updates to the NDR dataset are expected.

5.2.4. BIP! Scholar

Scope & Main Functionalities: BIP! Scholar is a platform that enables researchers to create profiles representing their research activities, enrich them with contextual information, and highlight different aspects of their research careers. The main objective of the platform is to offer profiles that cover a wide range of research activities, going beyond scientific publications. The platform leverages data from scholarly knowledge graphs (OpenAIRE Graph, Crossref, OpenCitations) and ORCID⁴³ to display custom reports containing lists of contributions and a variety of indicators that capture different aspects of the researchers' performance (e.g., productivity, impact, career stage) while considering their different roles in the respective works (according to the CRediT taxonomy). The platform also supports multiple ways to present (and download) researcher profiles, offering both traditional and innovative templates (e.g., narrative CV templates) aimed at being more responsible and inclusive. Finally, BIP! Scholar profiles can be dynamically tailored by the viewer to facilitate the examination of a researcher's career according to specific topics, roles or types of activity that may be of interest.

Implementation: Within the context of GraspOS, the platform was extended to (a) support multiple profile templates for researchers, including well-established templates for narrative CVs and the Openness Profile concepts developed by GraspOS experts, (b) provide more evidence on researchers' Open Science practices, and (c) offer appropriate visualisations. Important effort was devoted to the creation of a template editor for administrators that gives them the liberty to create highly customisable academic profile templates that can be used by researchers to create their own profiles.

Deviations: Initially, there was a plan to support the registration of academic profiles into the RAiD-based Openness Profile Registry. The implementation team has carried out an experimental deployment of the integration with this service; however, since the service is not yet production-ready (due to pending agreements), this integration has not yet been released

⁴³ ORCID: <https://orcid.org/>

in production. At the point when the Openness Profile Registry will become fully operational, the development team will implement the respective functionality.

Future plans: The implementation team aims to further extend the functionalities of the academic profile editor. Additionally, more profile templates will be supported by the platform. Finally, the implementation team will implement the connection to the Openness Profile Registry when this service becomes fully operational.

5.2.5. EOSC Accounting for Services

Scope & Main Functionalities: EOSC Accounting for Services⁴⁴ is a platform designed to efficiently collect, aggregate, and exchange metrics across various infrastructures, providers, and projects. The system provides a REST API, which accepts input from diverse resources, stores it in a database, and aggregates the incoming data. It also offers an intuitive user interface that allows clients to interact with the platform and access accounting data for specific time periods. All API resources are accessible only to authenticated clients, ensuring secure access to sensitive data.

The key functionalities offered by the EOSC Accounting Service include:

- Efficient collection, aggregation, and exchange of metrics
- REST API for input from diverse resources
- Database storage and aggregation of incoming data
- Intuitive user interface for accessing accounting data
- Secure access to sensitive data through authenticated clients.

The system provides a framework for organising and managing accounting data for specific projects, providers, or installations. It involves various roles, such as Project Admin, Provider Admin, and Installation Admin, each with a specific set of responsibilities.

One of the core components of the Accounting Service is Metrics, which are quantitative measures used to evaluate and monitor the performance or usage of a service. A Metric Definition specifies the type of metric being tracked. In this system, Metric and Unit Types are crucial for collecting and monitoring various metrics. A Metric Type determines how physical quantities are gathered over time, while a Unit Type defines and measures these quantities across different infrastructures, service providers, and projects. This framework enables users to collect and analyse data at various levels of detail and in different units of measurement.

This system could be extended in order to compute open science-related impact metrics, harvested from infrastructures' usage statistics. For instance, it could be applied to track the

⁴⁴ <https://api.devel.acc.argo.grnet.gr> and <https://argo.eu.github.io/argo-accounting>

number of users, and projects, helping to demonstrate how resources support broader collaboration by counting the researchers or institutions utilising the infrastructure, or to capture the geographical distribution of these users, illustrating the global reach and inclusivity of Open Science initiatives. Additionally, by measuring data transfer rates, the system could highlight the extent of data sharing and collaboration across different resources, services, and platforms, reflecting the project's contribution to Open Science.

Implementation: Within the context of GraspOS, the EOSC Accounting service demonstrates a proof of concept (PoC) showing the potential of the service to support Responsible Research Assessment (RRA). By integrating usage metrics from European and national publication repositories alongside HPC resource usage data (e.g., cpu and gpu core-hours), EOSC Accounting enables a multidimensional evaluation of research activity that encompasses scholarly impact, computational effort, and environmental sustainability. Persistent identifiers, such as ORCID, allow precise mapping of outputs and resource consumption to individual researchers and projects, paving the way for a longitudinal analysis, and data-driven decision-making at institutional and national levels. Looking ahead, the transformative implications of this model are significant. For computational research domains, this framework offers a way to recognise and reward computational effort and efficiency, not just output volume. For institutions and funders, it provides a mechanism to ensure that public investments in infrastructure translate into measurable, impactful, and traceable scientific outcomes. For EOSC and its stakeholders, it positions EOSC Accounting as a strategic enabler of infrastructure-aware, data-driven, and responsible research governance.

Deviations: The Proof of Concept conducted at TRUBA (Türkiye's National e-Infrastructure), an HPC center, demonstrated that the current user-based accounting model used by TRUBA—where each researcher operates under an individual account—limits full end-to-end integration with EOSC Accounting. This structure fragments usage records and prevents aggregation of core-hour consumption at the project level, constraining the ability to generate comprehensive and comparable metrics. Hence for the PoC, pre-processing scripts were required to associate authors with HPC usernames and to reformat usage data for analysis. Governance-related aspects such as GDPR-compliant anonymisation, institutional approvals, and procedures for metric submissions are also not yet fully defined, which limits scalability without further policy updates.

To overcome this limitation, TRUBA plans to revise its accounting mechanisms toward a project-based model, enabling accurate project-level reporting and improved alignment with EOSC Accounting for Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) workflows. This enhancement

will also facilitate more effective testing and validation of the mechanism within future integration activities.

Future plans: Future work will build upon the experience gained from the TRUBA PoC to generalise and operationalise the integration model across HPC centres. The adoption of project-based accounting models—where users operate under shared project accounts rather than individual ones—will enable project-level aggregation of resource usage and facilitate the linkage of computational activities with research products.

However, to enable this linkage effectively, a dedicated platform will be required through which users can supply information about the publications or studies associated with their HPC projects. This information can subsequently be updated when the related products are deposited in repositories (e.g., arXiv) or assigned Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) upon journal publication. Such a workflow will enable the matching of core-hour usage with research products, providing evidence-based insights into computational contributions to scientific outcomes. Even in HPC centres that already support project-based user structures, a mechanism for users to upload or register project-related publications may still be absent. In such cases, persistent identifier frameworks such as RAiD can serve as an intermediary mechanism for linking project metadata (e.g., DOIs, titles, contributors) with resource usage records.

Metadata collection will be enhanced by requesting ORCIDs and DOIs during account creation, with optional acknowledgements in publications (e.g., "We acknowledge TRUBA for 10,000 core-hours"). An optimised end-to-end workflow will automate metric collection from HPC and journal systems, transforming raw data (e.g., job logs, bibliometrics) into standardised EOSC schemas and enabling integrated queries for multidimensional RRA. Broader adoption across EOSC nodes will involve multi-tenancy enhancements, granular reporting (installation-, node-, project-, provider-level), and alignment with FAIR/RRA principles to promote sustainability, equity, and Open Science governance.

5.2.6. GoTriple Discovery Platform

Scope & Main Functionalities: GoTriple is a multilingual discovery platform tailored for the in-depth exploration of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research. It facilitates the discovery of scholarly content and fosters academic collaboration. From a single access point, researchers can find publications, research profiles and projects which are currently scattered across local repositories. The key features are the following:

- **Specific Search Engine for Social Sciences and Humanities:** Provides dedicated search capabilities specifically for the SSH community;

- **Multilingual Research Access:** Supports multiple languages, enabling users to find publications, engage with and contribute to international research dialogues;
- **Open Access Emphasis:** Offers a wealth of Open Access resources, reflecting a commitment to the principles of Open Science;
- **Intuitive Interface Design:** Features a straightforward and accessible design, enabling users to focus easily on the search;
- **Community and Collaboration:** Strengthens connections within SSH disciplines, promoting community-driven research and collaboration.

Implementation: The GoTriple service has been operational for several years, and its inclusion in GraspOS focused on leveraging its APIs within the GraspOS infrastructure to enable users to explore the diversity of resources available in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) domain. The main advantage of GoTriple as a data source lies in its ability to aggregate metadata from multiple sources, significantly reducing the time and effort required for users to retrieve and analyse SSH content. During the GraspOS project, GoTriple expanded to encompass more than 1,500 data sources and nearly 20 million documents, with outputs indexed in 11 languages. This growth has enhanced the platform's role as a central hub for multilingual and diverse SSH scholarship. As part of this work, several key resources were produced to support reuse and transparency: the GoTriple Workflow⁴⁵, published through SSHOC, the GoTriple Metadata Dataset⁴⁶ available on Zenodo, and a GitHub repository⁴⁷ containing code for extracting publication metadata (and, optionally, full texts) from the GoTriple API.

Deviations: No deviations identified at this point.

Future plans: The project will organise a webinar to discuss further potential uses of GoTriple in the context of Research Assessment, in collaboration with GRAPHIA (GA:101188018) and LUMEN (GA:101187940). GRAPHIA develops a knowledge graph for SSH, and it will explore its potential use for monitoring SSH and research assessment. While LUMEN will feature a specific discussion on the development of metrics for the LUMEN White Label Platform, based on GoTriple. In essence, the metrics approach will review how metrics can be developed responsibly in line with DORA and CoARA Recommendations.

⁴⁵ <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/3rVKH7>

⁴⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/15784401>

⁴⁷ <https://github.com/odoma-ch/gotriple-data-utils/blob/main/README.md>

5.2.7. Open Science Observatory

Scope & Main Functionalities: The Open Science Observatory⁴⁸ is a portal designed to facilitate access to Open Science indicators for policymakers, funders, and other organisations by combining and visualising information from all over Europe. It presents a collection of indicators and visualisations that help stakeholders to better understand the Open Science landscape in Europe across countries and subject areas. The platform assists in the monitoring and consequently enhancing Open Science policy uptake across various dimensions of interest, identifying weak spots and uncovering hidden potential. Based on the OpenAIRE Graph, and following Open Science principles and an evidence-based approach, the indicators provide timely and reliable insights into the evolution of Open Science in Europe, and support the promotion of good practices.

Implementation: At the start of GraspOS, the Open Science Observatory was already a stable and mature service, developed and maintained by OpenAIRE as part of its policy monitoring infrastructure. During the project, the Observatory itself was not directly used by any GraspOS pilot, which relied instead on more granular or domain-specific tools such as OpenAIRE MONITOR⁴⁹, CONNECT⁵⁰, or broader uses of the OpenAIRE Graph. However, data from the Observatory were indirectly exploited to support analysis and contextualisation activities, particularly in the evaluation of Open Science policy trends and their relationship with institutional practices. The experience gained through GraspOS highlighted that the quantitative indicators provided by the Observatory are most valuable when combined with qualitative evidence, such as surveys and interviews, to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of Open Science implementation. Separately, and as part of a different initiative, this integrated approach is being further explored within the EOSC Track⁵¹ project, which builds on OpenAIRE's previous experience while maintaining a clear separation of scope and funding. Consequently, the role of the Observatory within the OpenAIRE ecosystem is now evolving: its core datasets and indicator logic are being technically aligned and prepared for integration into the upcoming EOSC Open Science Observatory infrastructure, ensuring continuity of access while enabling richer analytical connections with other data sources⁵².

Deviations: The main deviation from the original plan is the limited direct use of the service by GraspOS pilots. While initial expectations foresaw potential exploitation for Open Science policy monitoring, the pilots' needs evolved towards institutional and thematic monitoring, better served by CONNECT and MONITOR. As a result, efforts were redirected from

⁴⁸ Open Science Observatory (OSO), <https://osobservatory.openaire.eu>

⁴⁹ <https://monitor.openaire.eu/>

⁵⁰ <https://connect.openaire.eu/>

⁵¹ EOSC Track: <https://www.openaire.eu/eosc-track-project>

⁵² EOSC Open Science Observatory data workflow and methodology, <https://www.eoscobservatory.eu/resources/data-workflow-and-methodology>

maintaining standalone dashboards to ensuring data interoperability and facilitating the transition of the Observatory's content into EOSC Observatory. No major technical issues occurred, and the service remained functional throughout the project.

Future plans: The Open Science Observatory is expected to be fully integrated into the EOSC Open Science Observatory as a data and analytics component, rather than maintained as a separate service. Future work will therefore focus on:

- Migrating existing datasets and indicators to the EOSC Open Science Observatory infrastructure;
- Enabling the combined use of Observatory data with qualitative evidence (e.g., survey and interview data) for research policy studies;
- Providing synthetic policy dashboards that combine evidence from Graph-based metrics and contextual information;
- Phasing out the current standalone portal, while ensuring continuity and accessibility of its datasets through the EOSC Open Science Observatory and other OpenAIRE services.

This transition reflects a strategic evolution: the Observatory's analytical capabilities will not disappear, but will become an integrated, interoperable layer supporting the broader EOSC and OpenAIRE ecosystem for Open Science monitoring and responsible research assessment.

5.2.8. OpenAIRE Broker

Scope & Main Functionalities. The OpenAIRE Broker is a notification service that enables content providers (such as repositories, Current Research Information Systems - CRIS, aggregators, knowledge graphs, and publishers) to complete and enrich the metadata of their registered scholarly works with information from the OpenAIRE Graph. This service effectively enhances the provider's content with up-to-date information that may be missing, thereby showcasing the openness, FAIRness, usage, and links to other records. The service is available to the end users through a registration to the OpenAIRE PROVIDE⁵³ service.

Through the **OpenAIRE PROVIDE**, data source managers can subscribe to different *enrichment topics* and receive **notifications** when new or improved metadata become available. The supported enrichments are:

- Additional Persistent Identifiers (e.g., DOIs);
- Links to funded projects;

⁵³ OpenAIRE PROVIDE: <https://provide.openaire.eu/home>

- ORCID identifiers for authors;
- Links to Open Access versions;
- Additional classification subjects (e.g., ACM, JEL, DDC);
- Abstracts identified in duplicate records;
- Missing publication dates.

Users can preview enrichments (up to 100 sample events per topic) and then subscribe programmatically or via the UI to receive full datasets of enrichments through the **Broker API**. Notifications are continuously updated as the Graph evolves, enabling repositories and CRIS systems to maintain **up-to-date, richer, and FAIRer metadata**. The Broker's APIs are open and free to use under a **CC-BY license**, and the service is operated 24/7 within the OpenAIRE infrastructure hosted at ICM (Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling, Poland).

Implementation: The service was already in a mature phase when the project started. In the context of GraspOS, routine maintenance, performance improvements have been performed. Although GraspOS pilots did not directly use the Broker as an individual service, they **benefited from the Graph enhancements** available in the OpenAIRE Graph.

Deviations: The main deviation from the initial plan concerns the direct adoption of the Broker service by the GraspOS pilots. Instead of individually subscribing to enrichment notifications, pilot partners accessed the OpenAIRE Graph as a whole.

Future plans: Building on the results of GraspOS, the next milestones for the OpenAIRE Broker focus on **expanding its coverage of the enhancements available in the OpenAIRE Graph** to better support data quality and assessment use cases:

- Implement **metadata validation alerts** (e.g., about compliance with the OpenAIRE Guidelines);
- Introduce **compliance history tracking** over time for data sources;
- Develop **new enrichment event types** (e.g., links to datasets, open peer review materials, software records);
- Strengthen the integration of the Broker with **OpenAIRE PROVIDE** and **Graph APIs** to offer richer analytics on enrichment coverage and data quality trends;
- Continue community engagement through webinars and API testing sessions with repository and CRIS managers.

5.2.9. OpenAIRE CONNECT

Scope & Main Functionalities: OpenAIRE CONNECT is a service providing research gateways for research initiatives, research infrastructures, research communities and networks that jointly would like to showcase their Open Science activities. These customised, on-demand gateways offer a sustainable platform for discovering, sharing, and curating research products (publication, data, software and other). Curators can customise the dashboards to match their specific needs, filtering and selecting information from the OpenAIRE Graph. CONNECT gateways can thus act as thematic or institutional portals, or as community dashboards, supporting a wide variety of use cases such as Open Science monitoring, project visibility, and research trend analysis. The service also enables programmatic access to the gateway contents via APIs, thus offering flexible integration with external systems and analytics pipelines.

Implementation: At the start of GraspOS, OpenAIRE CONNECT was already a mature and stable service, with operational gateways serving various universities, research infrastructures, thematic research networks, and European university alliances. Within GraspOS, maintenance and targeted functional extensions were implemented based on feedback collected from the pilots and their domain-specific needs. As reported in D5.2 – GraspOS Pilots: Implementation and Evaluation Results, CONNECT was employed by pilots in Computer Science, Social Sciences (OPERAS), and Agriculture to explore domain-specific applications of the OpenAIRE Graph and to filter, curate, and visualise research information relevant to their disciplinary contexts. Key activities included:

- **Selection and filtering of metadata** from the OpenAIRE Graph related to the pilots;
- Use of **text mining and semantic enrichment** to identify discipline-relevant research products and improve **topic clustering** (e.g., Fields of Science - FoS and UN's Sustainable development goals - SDGs);
- Testing **metadata integration workflows** with external systems (repositories, CRIS, or community discovery tools) to ensure interoperability and validation of data pipelines;
- Exploration of **API-based access** to support further analysis and automated updates of domain dashboards;
- Production and analysis of **metadata snapshots** dedicated to the pilots in support of responsible research assessment activities.

This work demonstrated how CONNECT can serve as a lightweight, yet powerful, tool to support evidence-based assessment and domain monitoring, leveraging the OpenAIRE Graph's open and enriched metadata.

In collaboration with the **SciLake project**⁵⁴ (GA:101058573), initial steps were also taken toward enhancing the quality of Field of Science indicators and topic classifications. As CONNECT builds upon the same underlying data infrastructure, these developments directly contribute to increasing the precision and thematic refinement of CONNECT gateways and APIs for future thematic pilots.

Deviations: A significant deviation from the original plan concerns the inclusion of OpenAIRE CONNECT within GraspOS. Initially, the service was not foreseen in the project's technical implementation, as pilots were expected to interact directly with the OpenAIRE Graph data or APIs. However, during the pilot phase, it became evident that a dedicated user interface was necessary to allow participants to filter data, and explore domain-specific outputs without relying on resource-greedy Graph data dumps or complex queries. As a result, OpenAIRE CONNECT was integrated into the project to serve as an intermediary layer, improving usability, accessibility, and interaction with the Graph. This adaptation provided a more efficient way for pilots to visualise and manage their data, ultimately enhancing engagement and the reproducibility of the GraspOS pilot results.

Future plans: Future work on OpenAIRE CONNECT will build upon the GraspOS experience and SciLake collaboration to enhance its analytical, thematic, and community-level capacity:

- Introduce **fine-grained Field of Science indicators** and **advanced topic classifications** derived from text-mining techniques;
- Improve **API endpoints** for domain, project, and funding-level analytics;
- Enhance the **filtering and visualisation options** within CONNECT gateways to enable **search and aggregation by subcommunity** (e.g., research groups, institutional clusters, or thematic subnetworks within a larger community);
- Enable tighter **integration with OpenAIRE MONITOR**, allowing CONNECT gateways to act as **interactive thematic dashboards**;
- Expand the offer of **custom CONNECT Gateways** for new communities and alliances emerging from GraspOS.

By combining Graph enrichment, community customisation, and fine-grained filtering, CONNECT will continue evolving as a core OpenAIRE service for community-driven Open Science monitoring and responsible assessment.

⁵⁴ <https://scilake.eu/>

5.2.10. OpenAIRE Graph

Scope & Main Functionalities: The OpenAIRE Graph is a free and open resource that brings together and interlinks hundreds of millions of metadata records from over 100k trusted data sources., covering research products (publications, datasets, software, etc.), projects, organizations, funders, and related entities. Launched in 2012 as one of the first research knowledge graphs, it has since grown into one of the world's largest and most authoritative sources for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The Graph is accessible to researchers, communities, institutions, companies, and citizens, enabling them to access research products and related information.

Metadata records are openly available under a CC-BY license, and accessible through a public API,⁵⁵ ensuring interoperability and reusability for both human and machine agents.

Implementation: The service was already in a mature phase when the project started. In the context of GraspOS, basic maintenance and targeted extensions (based on feedback from the GraspOS pilots) were anticipated as part of the implementation efforts. Within GraspOS, activities focused on targeted improvements and validation tasks to support the project's objectives of responsible and open research assessment. In particular:

- The Graph metadata model was extended to include new relationships between research products, metrics, and classifications relevant for assessment indicators;
- API alignment was performed to ensure compatibility with the GraspOS data model and API specification (as described in D4.2);
- The Graph provided the **data foundation** for all GraspOS pilots, enabling integration and testing of new assessment indicators;
- **Data validation and enrichment exercises**, carried out in collaboration with a partner university, focused on improving the **linkage between authors, affiliations, projects, and outputs**, and verifying **metadata consistency** across different data sources;
- These activities strengthened the **semantic relationships** within the Graph and improved its suitability for **institutional and disciplinary-level assessment use cases**;
- The **integration of BIP algorithms** (Bibliometric/Impact/Popularity) into the Graph's production pipeline added **citation-based indicators** — including *citation count*, *popularity*, *influence*, and *impulse* — that were tested for responsible use within the GraspOS pilots.

Another major advancement concerned the Person Entity, which is further developing and aligning with ORCID data to ensure accurate and persistent identification of individual researchers. This work is supporting the creation of verified and interoperable researcher

⁵⁵ <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/apis/graph-api/>

profiles, providing the data backbone for the MyResearchFolio⁵⁶ service. By strengthening person-level disambiguation and enriching author–organisation–output relationships, the Graph now offers a more reliable representation of researcher activities and contributions across systems and domains. Through these combined actions, the Graph evolved into a more accurate, semantically rich, and assessment-ready data infrastructure, supporting interoperability between institutional systems and OpenAIRE services.

Deviations: No significant deviations occurred. The implementation followed the planned low-intensity maintenance and validation approach. Instead of introducing large-scale structural changes, the project focused on **testing, feedback loops, and integration of pre-existing enhancements**, such as the BIP-based citation metrics, the improved affiliation mappings, and the new Person Entity. This ensured **continuity, data quality, and stability** while directly addressing the needs emerging from the pilots and partner validation work.

Future plans: Future development of the OpenAIRE Graph — in synergy with **SciLake** and follow-up OpenAIRE initiatives — will focus on:

- Extending the coverage of affiliation and citation information to better support responsible research assessment.
- Expanding **Person Entity functionalities**, ensuring closer **integration with ORCID** and enabling **cross-service interoperability** with MyResearchFolio and other researcher-centric tools;
- Consolidating and exposing **BIP-based citation and impact indicators** through public APIs;
- Enhancing **Field of Science (FoS) classifications** and **semantic enrichment** with machine learning and text-mining techniques;
- Supporting **fine-grained queries and analytics per person, community, or institution**;
- Maintaining the **FAIRness, openness, and sustainability** of the Graph as a shared European data backbone.

In this way, the OpenAIRE Graph will continue to underpin the open, verifiable, and responsible assessment of research across the GraspOS ecosystem and future Open Science initiatives.

⁵⁶ <https://myresearchfolio.openaire.eu/>

5.2.11. OpenAIRE Metadata Validator

Scope & Main Functionalities: The OpenAIRE Metadata Validator service is designed for content providers who wish to register their content with OpenAIRE. It allows them to verify that their content complies with the OpenAIRE guidelines and checks the quality of implementation of the OAI-PMH protocol⁵⁷. Content providers can access the service after logging into OpenAIRE PROVIDE⁵⁸. The provider's content will be regularly aggregated into the OpenAIRE Graph. OpenAIRE supports the registration of a wide range of sources, including institutional and thematic repositories listed in OpenDOAR⁵⁹, research data repositories in re3data⁶⁰, repositories in FAIRsharing⁶¹, Open Access e-journals, CRIS systems in euroCRIS DRIS, as well as aggregators and publishers. The OpenAIRE Metadata Validator service is implemented with configurable software that allows repository managers to customise validation options, such as the version of the OpenAIRE Guidelines to validate the content and the number of records or specific sets to be validated. This configurability facilitates adaptation whenever the OpenAIRE Guidelines or Metadata Validator service are updated, and allows similar validation services to be offered with custom rules and configurations. The service is available to the end users through a registration to the OpenAIRE PROVIDE⁶² service.

Implementation: At the beginning of GraspOS, the OpenAIRE Metadata Validator was already a mature, production-level component of the OpenAIRE infrastructure. Although it was not directly used by the GraspOS pilots, it indirectly supported their work through its integration in the OpenAIRE Graph ingestion and enrichment workflows. The Validator contributes to the continuous quality assurance of metadata aggregated in the Graph, meaning that the datasets and publications analysed by the pilots — including those retrieved from national repositories such as HAL⁶³ (France) — benefited from this validation process before being exposed in the thematic dashboards. As a result, even though pilots did not explicitly interact with the Validator interface, their feedback on data completeness and interoperability indirectly validated the performance of the service itself, providing valuable insights for further improvement. In parallel, the service is being extended for use by additional partners, including TÜBİTAK, as part of ongoing OpenAIRE collaborations on metadata validation and FAIRness assessment. Within GraspOS, the Validator was also foreseen for potential extension with domain-specific FAIRness configurations, aimed at calculating both record-level and aggregated metrics for repositories, funders, and institutions.

⁵⁷ OAI-PMH protocol: <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

⁵⁸ <https://provide.openaire.eu/>

⁵⁹ <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/opensoar/>

⁶⁰ <https://www.re3data.org/>

⁶¹ <https://fairsharing.org/>

⁶² OpenAIRE PROVIDE: <https://provide.openaire.eu/home>

⁶³ <https://hal.science/?lang=en>

Deviations: The main deviation from the initial plan is that the Metadata Validator was not actively used by pilots, as their metadata quality checks were performed indirectly through the OpenAIRE Graph. However, this indirect usage proved beneficial, as it demonstrated the Validator's role in improving upstream data quality and ensuring reliable integration of metadata into pilot dashboards. The focus thus shifted from user-driven validation to system-level validation within the Graph ingestion pipeline, supporting a broader and more automated approach to metadata curation.

Future plans: Future developments for the OpenAIRE Metadata Validator will focus on:

- Introducing configurable FAIRness validation modules, with indicators at both record and data source level;
- Expanding support for domain-specific metadata profiles, particularly for disciplines covered by GraspOS pilots;
- Enhancing integration with OpenAIRE PROVIDE and the Broker, allowing providers to receive unified feedback on validation and enrichment;
- Supporting external partners (e.g., TÜBİTAK) in adopting the Validator for national infrastructures;
- Extending its role as a quality assurance backbone within the OpenAIRE Graph ingestion pipeline;
- Collaborating with the OSTRails⁶⁴ project, which is further developing the FAIRness assessment layer for indicators derived from metadata validation according to the FAIR principles. The resulting data will be integrated into the FAIR Score computed by the Metadata Validator and delivered as part of the OpenAIRE MONITOR indicators, enhancing cross-service consistency and comparability of FAIRness metrics.

Through these developments, the OpenAIRE Metadata Validator will continue to play a central role in ensuring **data quality, interoperability, and FAIRness** across the OpenAIRE ecosystem and its future integrations with European Open Science infrastructures.

5.2.12. OpenAIRE MONITOR

Scope & Main Functionalities: OpenAIRE MONITOR is a service that generates well-documented, timely, and accurate monitoring indicators of research activities for funders, research initiatives, and organisations by creating personalised, on-demand, and configurable online dashboards. All information is aggregated, processed, and provided by the OpenAIRE Graph. The OpenAIRE MONITOR aims to create a comprehensive and relevant set of metrics, as well as composite and advanced indicators to build funder, institutional and

⁶⁴ <https://ostrails.eu/>

research infrastructure monitoring dashboards. It offers functionalities such as external (public stakeholders) vs internal (team members) dashboards, supported by role-based access control that distinguishes between *Managers* (with administrative rights to configure dashboards, manage visibility, and invite users) and *Members* (with access to restricted dashboards and indicators), along with authentication and visibility modes (public, restricted, and private). In addition, MONITOR enables downloading visualisations and datasets, provides advanced filtering functionalities and includes direct links to underlying research products, with the aim of being a one-stop shop for the monitoring, policymaking, analysis and reporting needs of stakeholders.

Implementation: At the beginning of GraspOS, OpenAIRE MONITOR was already a mature service supporting several institutional and national dashboards. Within the project, MONITOR was extended with new functionalities and indicators to support responsible research assessment in the context of the GraspOS pilots.

In particular:

- New templates and dashboard views were created to represent thematic and institutional perspectives, aligned with the pilots in Computer Science, Social Sciences (OPERAS), and Agriculture.
- Custom indicators were developed to explore openness, interdisciplinarity, collaboration patterns, and societal impact, derived from OpenAIRE Graph data;
- Integration with the Metadata Validator enabled the inclusion of FAIRness indicators and the FAIR Score, combining metadata quality information with research output-level metrics.
- MONITOR dashboards were used as prototypes for institutional and thematic monitors, offering visualisations of data completeness, output typology, and links to funding projects.
- Close collaboration with the University of Bologna contributed to refining several visualisations and indicator definitions, improving data source coverage, and consolidating the data backbone supporting the monitoring dashboards;
- A pilot case study with the University of Belgrade demonstrated MONITOR's flexibility by introducing custom visualisations that distinguished Green Open Access publications from other access types. By analysing repository data (e.g., *trapist.rcub.bg.ac.rs* and *spira*) and integrating embargoed-access metadata from the OpenAIRE Graph, the Belgrade MONITOR dashboard improved transparency and tracking accuracy of institutional Open Science practices.

The experience gained through GraspOS demonstrated MONITOR's capacity to bridge open data, metadata quality, and policy evaluation, positioning it as a key infrastructure for responsible and open research assessment.

Deviations: The main deviation from the original plan concerns the focus of the MONITOR pilots. While initial expectations included use cases involving funder-oriented dashboards, the pilots that effectively adopted MONITOR were primarily institutional and thematic, reflecting the needs of the participating partners. This shift in focus did not impact the overall objectives of GraspOS but influenced the type of indicators and visualisations that were prioritised and tested. Nevertheless, funder-related indicators and datasets within MONITOR were reviewed and refined based on feedback collected through the GraspOS community and a series of community calls with external stakeholders. This ensured that the service continued to address the requirements of multiple user groups, aligning institutional and funder perspectives under a common framework for open and responsible research assessment.

Future plans: Future work on **OpenAIRE MONITOR** will focus on strengthening its analytical capacity and ensuring a balanced approach across institutional, thematic, and funder perspectives. The next development steps will include:

- **Rebalancing and expanding funder-oriented dashboards**, refining indicators and visualisations based on feedback collected during the GraspOS activities and stakeholder consultations;
- **Improving indicator accuracy and visual clarity**, in continued collaboration with partner universities that contributed to testing and data validation;
- **Integrating FAIRness metrics** derived from the Metadata Validator and OSTrails⁶⁵ project into a consolidated **FAIR Score**, enabling more comprehensive reporting on research output quality and openness;
- **Enhancing data coverage and interpretability**, ensuring that MONITOR dashboards provide clear and actionable insights into Open Science practices across disciplines and institutions;
- **Introducing qualitative annotations and contextual notes** to complement quantitative indicators, allowing users to add narrative explanations and contextual information in line with the principles promoted by **CoARA**.

These developments will reinforce MONITOR's role as a reliable and transparent platform for monitoring Open Science policies and practices, supporting evidence-based and context-aware responsible research assessment.

⁶⁵ <https://ostrails.eu/>

5.2.13. OpenAIRE MyResearchFolio

Scope & Main Functionalities: OpenAIRE MyResearchFolio, formerly named Researcher Profile, is a new service being developed as part of the GraspOS project. It is designed to be a comprehensive platform that showcases a researcher's academic and professional career advancements. This profile not only displays traditional research products such as publications, data, and software but also highlights the researcher's broader academic activities and entrepreneurial endeavours to create a personalised and updated career pathway.

In addition to a detailed overview of their contributions, the profile features metrics and indicators offering valuable insights of researchers' aggregated impact, productivity, and compliance with OS practices. MyResearchFolio aims to help researchers increase their visibility, track their performance, and demonstrate their adherence to OS principles.

Implementation: The service is currently under active development. Within GraspOS, efforts focus on refining the Person Entity in OpenAIRE Graph, integrating ORCID interoperability, and designing the first prototype interface for visualising researcher-level contributions. Feedback on the prototype had been collected during dissemination activities. A mature release of MyResearchFolio is expected by the end of the project, providing an interactive and transparent environment for researcher assessment and visibility

Deviations: The main deviation concerns the origin of the indicators implemented in the service. Rather than being directly derived from the initial internal framework, most indicators were inspired and adapted from the OPUS⁶⁶ and PathOS⁶⁷ projects, as well as from the landscape analysis of research assessment services conducted in WP2 and WP3. This approach ensured methodological consistency with ongoing European initiatives and enabled the definition of robust, reusable components for the platform. Another deviation was that the pilots were unable to conduct a thorough evaluation of the service due to unforeseen delays in the service's implementation.

Future plans: Future work will complete the development and integration of MyResearchFolio within the OpenAIRE ecosystem. Next steps include finalising the Person Entity, adding qualitative annotation features to complement quantitative metrics, and expanding visual analytics to display collaboration networks, thematic focus, and career progression. Once fully deployed, it will serve as an open and interoperable portfolio platform supporting responsible and contextual researcher assessment. Some GraspOS partners had expressed the will to continue the pilots after the end of the project.

⁶⁶ <https://opusproject.eu/>

⁶⁷ <https://pathos-project.eu/>

Delays in Implementation and Testing: Certain delays in the implementation and integration of specific components affected the planned timeline of the MyResearchFolio service, resulting in limited testing by some pilot partners. These delays were primarily related to the ongoing development of technical dependencies and the refinement of interoperability functionalities. Until now, the service has not been fully tested within the pilot environments. Despite these constraints, preliminary feedback obtained during early demonstrations has been incorporated into the subsequent development cycle to support the completion of a stable and fully functional release.

5.2.14. OpenAIRE ScholeXplorer

Scope & Main Functionalities: ScholeXplorer is a service that provides access to the largest collection of Open Access citations between articles and datasets and between datasets themselves, as exposed by Crossref⁶⁸, DataCite⁶⁹, EMBL-EBI⁷⁰, and OpenAIRE⁷¹. Links (and objects) are provided by data sources managed by publishers, data centres, or other organisations providing services to store and manage links between data sets and publications. ScholeXplorer aggregates link metadata harvested from the data sources and out of these, it builds harmonised and deduplicated graphs of scholarly objects. The graph is openly accessible via search REST APIs that return links in Scholix format.

Implementation: The service was already in a mature phase when the project started. In the context of GraspOS, basic maintenance and targeted extensions (based on feedback from the GraspOS pilots) were performed as part of the implementation efforts. During the project, activities focused on maintenance and incremental updates to ensure alignment with the evolving OpenAIRE Graph and compatibility with the GraspOS data model and APIs (see D4.2). The service indirectly supported pilot work by improving **linking accuracy** between research data and related publications.

Deviations: No major deviations occurred. Efforts focused primarily on ensuring data harmonisation and interoperability, rather than on extending new functionalities.

Future plans: Future work will aim to enhance the completeness and accuracy of dataset-publication links, improve interoperability with other Open Science services, and extend API capabilities for large-scale data reuse and citation analysis within the OpenAIRE ecosystem. Collaboration with OpenCitations will further strengthen the integration and linking of citation data with research products from the OpenAIRE Graph, improving coverage,

⁶⁸ <https://www.crossref.org/>

⁶⁹ <https://datacite.org/>

⁷⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ebisearch/about>

⁷¹ <https://explore.openaire.eu/>

transparency, and reusability of scholarly relationships across infrastructures. Although not always directly used by end users as a standalone service, ScholeXplorer plays a key background role in supporting the indicators and dashboards of OpenAIRE MONITOR, ensuring that citation and linkage data are accurate and up to date across the ecosystem.

5.2.15. OpenAIRE UsageCounts

Scope & Main Functionalities: OpenAIRE's UsageCounts service tracks and aggregates usage activity from a distributed network of Open Science content providers-repositories, Open Access e-journals, CRIS systems, and aggregators-to produce comparable, COUNTER-aligned⁷² metrics such as item downloads and metadata views. Results are exposed through OpenAIRE PROVIDE⁷³, OpenAIRE EXPLORE⁷⁴ and feed usage indicators into the OpenAIRE Graph⁷⁵ and OpenAIRE MONITOR⁷⁶ for analysis alongside bibliometrics, providing early signals of uptake that complement citation-based measures. Designed with GDPR-aware handling of sensitive data and an emphasis on interoperability, UsageCounts enables stakeholders to track, benchmark, and evidence the reach and engagement of research from the moment it is accessed.

Implementation: The service was already in a mature phase when the project started. In the context of GraspOS, basic maintenance and targeted extensions were implemented based on feedback from the GraspOS pilots. UsageCounts data indirectly supported several pilot activities by enriching the underlying information used for monitoring research products and their impact.

Deviations: No deviations occurred. Given the maturity of the service, the focus of the work shifted slightly toward consolidating and improving the data quality, consistency, interoperability and integration with other OpenAIRE components, rather than on introducing new functionalities. Efforts concentrated on harmonising usage data ingestion and reporting workflows, ensuring smooth integration with the OpenAIRE services. This prioritisation strengthened the reliability and reusability of the collected metrics, laying the foundation for future expansion.

Future plans: Future activities will focus on enhancing data harmonisation and broadening coverage across repositories and publishers. Plans include exploring new indicators of

⁷² <https://www.countermetrics.org/>

⁷³ <https://provide.openaire.eu>

⁷⁴ <https://explore.openaire.eu/>

⁷⁵ <https://graph.openaire.eu>

⁷⁶ <https://monitor.openaire.eu>

research uptake and refining aggregation methods to improve accuracy, interoperability, and reuse within the OpenAIRE ecosystem.

5.2.16. OpenCitations Data

Scope & Main Functionalities. OpenCitations has been established as a fully free and open infrastructure to provide access to global scholarly bibliographic and citation data. It enables several key benefits:

- Fairness: OpenCitations removes the need for institutions and independent scholars to pay exorbitant fees annually (that most of them cannot afford) for commercial access to their own scholarly data, making access more equitable.
- Reuse: Since there are no licence restrictions, and all data are provided under CC0, users can republish and reuse the citation data for any purpose.
- Research assessment: OpenCitations provides open data that can be used in national and international research evaluation exercises, making these activities transparent and reproducible.
- Governance: The community is directly involved in the evolution of the infrastructure, ensuring that it meets the needs of its users.

Implementation: The service was already in a mature phase when the project started. In the context of GraspOS, basic maintenance and targeted extensions (based on feedback from the GraspOS pilots) were carried out as part of the implementation efforts. In particular, following discussions with project partners, an additional operation named “venue-citation-count” was added to the OpenCitations Index API⁷⁷ enabling users to retrieve citation counts for all bibliographic entities published in a specific journal (identified by ISSN). Also, recently we have revised the ingestion workflow^{78,79}, and we have ingested new citation data from Crossref, DataCite, OpenAIRE, NIH-OCC, and JaLC, resulting in having more than 2.2 billion citations in our collections. Finally, similarly to other GraspOS data services, the API is being adapted to ensure compatibility with the GraspOS data model and API specification (see D4.2).

Deviations: No deviations from the original plan.

Future plans: The SKG-IF export format for the OpenCitations API will be implemented by the end of the project. In the future, OpenCitations will also provide a new API endpoint compliant with the SKG-IF Open API specification.

⁷⁷ <https://w3id.org/oc/index/api/v2>

⁷⁸ https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00292

⁷⁹ <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2408.02321>

5.2.17. Openness Profile Registry

Scope & Main Functionalities: The Openness Profile Registry, a new service, is part of the SCOPE+i Framework developed within the GraspOS project. The main ambition of the Openness Profile is to enable exposure of OS activities as an independent traceable information entity, leading to a more diverse consideration of Open Science in research and related assessment. The diversity of Open Science contributions is catered for through flexible ingestion of different types of entries, including quantitative and qualitative information. Qualitative information, for example captured through narrative description, can be used to frame how contributions are understood and how they can be assessed within a particular community, which facilitates structured and evidence-based input that supports research assessment. The Openness Profile provides a dedicated narrative field for users to contextualize their contributions to Open Science. Other narrative templates can be supported by the Openness Profile. The Openness Profile can also be used in assessment contexts, either directly or as a general-purpose portfolio. In direct use cases, OS contributions recorded in an Openness Profile can be integrated into local assessment infrastructures. Alternatively, the Openness Profile can function as a portfolio of all relevant contributions —OS-related or otherwise—for a specific assessment event.

Implementation: The Openness Profile Registry is a new service being developed as part of the GraspOS project. In the context of this project, an Openness Profile will be implemented via a Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) service point for piloting the service. Each registered Openness Profile will be assigned a persistent identifier and a metadata record, to ensure long-term accessibility and make the information suitable for public use. While a user interface is available for administering access and compiling content (useful for smaller tasks), the service is ideally integrated into local platforms via API.

Deviations: The scope has been expanded by enabling the Openness Profile to also function as a generic assessment portfolio for all relevant contributions—OS-related or otherwise—for a specific assessment event. Whereas the APP (see above) limits its content to the planning and design of the assessment protocol, the Openness Profile can serve as a portfolio for collecting the researcher contributions that will be assessed. This creates a separation between the assessment planning and design information (APP) and the contributions to be assessed (OP), which have a higher threshold for privacy (e.g., GDPR). In both cases, Assessment Protocol Portfolios and Openness Profiles can be hierarchically linked. For instance, linked information may share a common landing page and be accessible through an API.

Future plans: The current SCOPE+i services—comprising the Openness Profile Registry and the Assessment Protocol Portfolio Registry—already incorporate a mapping to the existing

RAiD metadata schema elements used to describe an assessment event. Looking ahead⁸⁰, we propose extending the RAiD metadata schema to better accommodate the specific requirements of research assessment. The introduction of additional fields would enable more comprehensive cataloguing of assessment projects, including details on the scope of the assessment as well as the data sources and metrics employed. Such an extension would strengthen interoperability and support greater transparency and comparability across assessment practices.

5.2.18. PRISM

Scope & Main Functionalities: The Peer Review Information Service for Monographs (PRISM) gives publishers the opportunity to display information about their peer review procedures in a standardised way and enables inclusion of this information as part of the book's metadata in the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB). PRISM contributes to building trust in Open Access book publishing by improving transparency around the quality assurance process. The key features are the following:

- *Title-Level Detail:* Provides specific information about the peer review process applied to each publication, directly on the DOAB platform;
- *Controlled Vocabulary:* Uses a standardised set of terms to describe their peer review processes, promoting consistency and clarity;
- *Catalogue-Level Overview:* Demonstrates transparency across a publisher's catalogue by showing the peer review processes that their titles undergo;
- *API Integration:* Provides data accessibility through the DOAB API, allowing for easy inclusion in library databases and search tools.

Implementation: PRISM is also available and operational as part of EOSC. Its inclusion in GraspOS is related to the valorisation of peer review practices in the expanding criteria and processes related to RRA. Similar to OPERAS Metrics, PRISM supports the inclusion of Open Access books in research assessment processes by increasing the transparency of the quality assurance process behind their publication. The integration of PRISM within GraspOS has successfully achieved its initial objectives, particularly the registration of PRISM as a service and widget within the GraspOS infrastructure. To further elaborate on this integration and its relevance for Responsible Research Assessment, a dedicated webinar⁸¹ was delivered to present PRISM and demonstrate how it can be used in research assessment contexts. The session highlighted how PRISM contributes to Responsible Research Assessment by making peer review processes visible, standardised, and interoperable within the GraspOS

⁸⁰ see D2.3 SCOPE+i Framework (forthcoming).

⁸¹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iD9QlywL_6w

infrastructure. This milestone ensures that PRISM can now interoperate within the broader GraspOS ecosystem, enhancing the transparency of Open Access books. From a technical point of view, we successfully designed and implemented an API-based workflow to enable the extraction, transformation, and sharing of metadata for all open access books containing a PRISM record. This workflow supports the creation of customised metadata exports based on defined criteria such as subject, language, or publication type, and delivers them in multiple interoperable formats suitable for Open Science infrastructures. The exported datasets have been made openly available through Zenodo, ensuring persistent identifiers, accessibility, and long-term preservation.

Deviations: Due to resource limitation and scheduling issues, the SKG-IF-compliant API specification, which GraspOS partners have contributed to, will not be implemented by PRISM by the end of the project.

Future plans: The API specification will be further discussed as part of ongoing efforts to standardise and expand the service, with the goal of establishing an API extension point at the earliest possible opportunity. The team will explore ways to automate the extraction of metadata records containing PRISM information and to implement a mechanism for periodic updates and integration with the GraspOS infrastructure, including the creation of a dedicated Zenodo entry as part of this process.

5.3. Code Repositories and Documentation

Table 6 outlines the code repositories, the demonstrators (if any), and the documentation resources available for the array of services that are currently available by the GraspOS infrastructure.

Table 6 Code repositories and documentation of the GraspOS services

Component	Code repository	Current deployment	Documentation
Assessment Protocol Registry (RAiD)	https://github.com/au-research/raid-au	N/A	API: https://api.demo.raid.org.au/swagger-ui/index.html Metadata Schema: https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/
BIP! DB	https://github.com/ath-enarc/Bip-Ranker	https://bip-api.imsi.ath-enarc.gr/documentation	https://github.com/ath-enarc/Bip-Ranker/blob/main/README.md

BIP! NDR	https://github.com/athenarc/bip-ndr-workflow	N/A	https://github.com/athenarc/bip-ndr-workflow/blob/main/README.md
BIP! Scholar	<p>Implementation of indicators: https://github.com/athenarc/bip-scholar-indicators</p> <p>Front-end is part of the BIP! Services code: https://github.com/athenarc/bip-services</p>	https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/scholar	https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/site/indicators#Researcher-level Indicators
EOSC Accounting for Services	https://github.com/ARGOeu/argo-accounting	https://api.devel.acc.argo.grnet.gr	https://argoeu.github.io/argo-accounting/
GoTriple Discovery Platform	https://github.com/odoma-ch/gotriple-data-utils	<p>Website: https://www.gotriple.eu</p> <p>Metadata Dataset (using the Github extraction process): https://zenodo.org/records/15784401</p>	https://github.com/odoma-ch/gotriple-data-utils/blob/main/README.md
Open Science Observatory	https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/open-science-observatory-ui.git	https://osobservatory.openaire.eu/home	https://osobservatory.openaire.eu/methodology
OpenAIRE Broker	<p>https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-hadoop</p> <p>https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-applications</p> <p>https://github.com/openaire/broker-commandline-client</p>	https://provide.openaire.eu (part of the OpenAIRE PROVIDE)	<p>https://graph.openaire.eu/develop/broker.html</p> <p>https://api.openaire.eu/broker/swagger-ui/index.html</p>
OpenAIRE Connect	https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/connect	https://connect.openaire.eu/	https://connect.openaire.eu/about/learn-how

OpenAIRE Graph	https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-hadoop	https://graph.openaire.eu/	https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/
OpenAIRE Metadata Validator	https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/metadata-validator-ui https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/uoa-validator-api https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/validator-engine	http://duffy.di.uoa.gr:5100/	Not available yet It is a tool built and based on the OpenAIRE Guidelines http://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/
OpenAIRE Monitor	https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/monitor https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/monitor-dashboard	https://monitor.openaire.eu/	https://monitor.openaire.eu/about https://monitor.openaire.eu/methodology/methodological-approach https://monitor.openaire.eu/methodology/terminology https://monitor.openaire.eu/indicators/themes https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.funder_dashboard/overview
OpenAIRE My ResearchFolio (prev. known as Researcher Profile)	MaDgIK/uoa-researcher-service - Gitea MaDgIK/researcher-profile - Gitea	https://myresearchfolio.openaire.eu/	N/A
OpenAIRE ScholeXplorer	https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-a	https://scholexplorer.openaire.eu/	https://scholexplorer.openaire.eu/documenta

	pplications/src/branch/master/apps/schoexplorer-api		tion
OpenAIRE UsageCounts	https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDglK/usage-counts	Incorporated into OpenAIRE PROVIDE	https://usagecounts.openaire.eu/
OpenCitations Data	All repository containing software used to run the infrastructure and ingest citation data can be found at https://github.com/opencitations/	https://opencitations.net	Data: https://download.opencitations.net/ API: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OpenCitations Index: https://w3id.org/oc/index/api/v2 • OpenCitations Meta: https://w3id.org/oc/meta/api/v1
Openness Profile Registry (RAiD)	https://github.com/au-research/raid-au	N/A	API: https://api.demo.raid.org.au/swagger-ui/index.html Metadata Schema: https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/
PRISM	If you want to display PRISM information on your own website, you can deploy the PRISM widget. The documentation can be found here: https://github.com/trilobiet/prism-widget .	Metadata extraction through this link. Supports isolating books with PRISM record: https://www.doabooks.org/en/librarians/metadata-harvesting-and-content-dissemination	Generic documentation on how a publisher can join DOAB/PRISM: https://doabooks.org/en/publishers/documentation

6. Conclusions

The GraspOS project has aimed to enhance research assessment practices by embedding Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) principles and Open Science values into practical, interoperable solutions. To this end, the project has delivered a comprehensive suite of tools and services that support transparent, inclusive, and evidence-based evaluation processes across diverse research domains.

This deliverable has presented the main functionalities and implementation details of these tools and services, demonstrating their role in supporting evaluators, institutions, and research communities in recognising a broader range of outputs and contributions. Collectively, they provide the technological foundation for an open and responsible research assessment ecosystem.

As the project approaches its conclusion, the developed components have reached a mature and operational state, with documentation, code repositories, and demonstrators openly available for reuse and further integration by the wider community. These outcomes represent a sustainable contribution to the advancement of responsible and transparent research assessment.